

COMPUTATION OF PLASTICITY INDEX OF INORGANIC CLAY USING FIRST AND SECOND NORM OF THE IDEALISED FALL CONE FLOW CURVE

Gerald Maregesi

Email: gerald.maregesi@aesl.co.tz

ABSTRACT

A model of computing the plasticity index of inorganic soil using the ratio of the second norm (Euclidian norm) to the first norm (Manhattan distance) of the idealized fall cone flow curve is proposed. The model was developed using 204 controlled Atterberg limit test results of inorganic soils and validated using 74 Atterberg limit test results collected from the literature. The model computes the plasticity index of the inorganic soils within the statistical testing bound of ± 8 .

INTRODUCTION

The plasticity index of soil is the arithmetic difference between the liquid and plastic limits. The liquid limit can be determined using two methods, namely the Casagrande cup (BS 1377:part 2:1990, AASHTO T89-2002) or the fall cone method, which, according to the BS 1377:part 2:1900, is the preferred method. The thread rolling method is used to determine the plastic limit (BS 1377:Part 2:1990, AASHTO T90-2000). The Casagrande cup method of determining the liquid limit is subjective since it depends mainly on the operator's judgment. The fall cone method was developed to overcome the reliance on the operator to make judgments during liquid limit testing. The thread rolling method for determining the plastic limit is very subjective; the test results largely depend on the operator's skill in rolling the soil to form a 3 mm ellipsoidal thread and judging the crumbling moisture content of the ellipsoidal thread. Therefore, the determination of the plastic limit has been subjected to a number of research seeking to establish an alternative method whose results are not affected by the operator's judgment.

Towner (1973), Harison (1988), and Feng (2002) proposed that the moisture content corresponding to 2 mm of British fall cone penetration represents the plastic limit of the soil. A method of determining the plasticity index using the fall cone index or slope

of the fall cone has also been proposed (Prakash *et al.* (1999), Maregesi (2022, 2023)).

This paper presents a model that can be used to compute the plasticity index of most of the inorganic soil using the ratio of the Euclidian distance (second norm) to the Manhattan distance (first norm) from the original coordinate (0,0) to the liquid limit coordinates (LL,20). The model was developed using 204 controlled Atterberg limit test results carried out during this study and validated using 74 Atterberg limit test results collected from the literature. The proposed model was found to compute the plasticity index within the statistical testing bound ± 8 reported by O'Kelly (2018).

DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL FOR COMPUTING PLASTIC LIMIT

The fall cone curve for determination of the liquid limit is normally modeled as linear within the penetration range of 20 ± 5 mm. However, the fall cone curve at lower moisture content and its corresponding penetration values are non-linear. Practically, it is possible to establish a moisture-penetration relationship up to a penetration value of about 3 mm; below this penetration value, it is impossible to determine the penetration of the soil. For the purpose of this study, it is hypothesized that as the moisture content decreases toward zero, the fall cone penetration also decreases toward zero (Maregesi, 2023). Therefore, the fall cone curve can be idealized to have a penetration value of zero at zero moisture content. Thus, the liquid limit of the soil can be treated as a position vector with a coordinate of (LL,20). Figure 1 shows the idealized moisture-penetration curve for silty clay soil with a liquid limit of 30. The idealized flow curve, which connects the original coordinate (0,0) and the liquid limit at coordinate (LL,20), can be treated as a position vector with a horizontal component equal to the liquid limit and a vertical component equal to the fall cone penetration at the liquid limit, i.e., 20 mm.

Figure 1: Moisture-penetration relationship and idealized curve for silty clay soil

Treating the idealized flow curve as a position vector with horizontal and vertical components, as shown in Figure 1, 204 Atterberg limits test results of inorganic soils, including bentonites with a wide range of liquid limits, plastic limits, and plasticity index, were analyzed. The liquid limit ranged from 20 to 338 with an average of 90, the plastic limit ranged from 10 to 61 with an average of 25, and the plasticity index ranged from 2 to 76. The box plot in Figure 2 shows the summary and the distribution of the Atterberg limit data used during this study.

The analysis of the Atterberg limit test results using an idealized flow curve indicates that the soil's plasticity index is highly correlated to the ratio of the second norm (Euclidian norm - L_2 norm) to the first norm (Manhattan distance). The Euclidian norm (L_2 norm) is computed using Equation 1.

$$||L||_2 = \sqrt{LL^2 + 20^2} \dots (1)$$

The Manhattan distance (L_1 norm) is computed from Equation 2.

$$||L||_1 = LL + 20 \dots (2)$$

Figure 2: The summary of the Atterberg limit data used for the development of the model

Figure 3 shows the relationship between the Euclidian norm (L_2 norm) ratio and the Manhattan distance (L_1 norm). It can be seen that the distance ratio is highly correlated to the plasticity index, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination of R^2 of 0.995. The relationship is fitted using a rational function, as shown in Equation 3.

$$I_p = \frac{-31.4591 + 46.6667x}{1 - 1.3813x + 0.3951x^2} \dots (3)$$

Where x is the ratio of the second norm to the first norm, as shown in Equation 4, I_p is the plasticity index.

$$x = \frac{||L||_2}{||L||_1} = \frac{\sqrt{LL^2 + 20^2}}{LL + 20} \dots (4)$$

Combining equations 3 and 4 results in equation 5.

$$I_p = \frac{-31.4591 + \frac{46.6667\sqrt{400 + LL^2}}{20 + LL}}{1 - \frac{1.3813\sqrt{400 + LL^2}}{20 + LL} + \frac{0.3951(400 + LL^2)}{(20 + LL)^2}} \dots \dots (5)$$

Equation 5 shows that the plasticity index of the inorganic soil can be computed using the liquid limit as the sole predictor variable. Therefore, the plasticity index of inorganic clay, in most cases, is a function of the liquid limit of the soil.

Figure 3: the relationship between the ratio of Euclidean norm to the first norm and the plasticity index ($R^2=0.995$)

COMPUTATION OF SOIL PLASTICITY INDEX USING THE MODEL

The plasticity index of 204 soils (including bentonite) tested during this investigation was computed using Equation 3. There is a very close agreement between the determined and computed plasticity indexes, as evidenced by the residual plot analysis plot shown in Figures 4, 5, 6, and 7. Figure 4 shows the residual, which is the arithmetic difference between the determined plasticity index and the computed plasticity index, from which it can be seen that the residuals are evenly distributed above and below the x-axis with no

discernible trends, suggesting that the proposed model fits the data reasonably well. The QQ plot shown in Figure 6 also confirms that the residual is normally distributed since all points are plotted within the 95% confidence interval band of the best-fit line. Figure 7, which shows the residual histogram plot, also confirms that the residual is normally distributed with a zero mean. The statistical testing bound of ± 8 is also plotted on the same graph, from which it can be seen that 201 test results out of 204 test results plots within the statistical testing bound.

Figure 5 shows the comparison between the determined and the computed plasticity index with statistical testing bound plotted on the same graph, from which it can be seen that the results plot within the statistical testing bound. The best-fit curve for the determined versus the computed plasticity index indicates that the results are highly correlated, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.996.

Figure 4: Residual plot showing the difference between the determined plasticity index and the computed plasticity index

Figure 5: Comparison between determined plasticity index and computed plasticity index ($R^2=0.995$)

Figure 7: Residual histogram

Figure 6: QQ plot of the residual

Figure 8: The liquid limit and plasticity index with a best-fit line using Equation 5

VALIDATION OF THE MODEL USING DATA FROM THE LITERATURE

The proposed model of computing the plasticity index of inorganic soil was validated using 74 Atterberg limit data collected from literature published by Kayabali *et al.* (2016), O'Kelly *et al.* (2018), and Sharma *et al.* (2003). The residual plot shown in Figures 8 and 9 indicates that the proposed model computes the plasticity index of the organic soil within the statistical testing bound, as evidenced by the fact that 73 of 74 of the test results were found to be within the statistical testing bound of ± 8 .

Figure 9: Residual plot of the data used for model validation

LIMITATION OF THE MODEL

Although the proposed model can be used to compute the plasticity index of the inorganic soil within the statistical testing bound of ± 8 , it can only be used to compute the plasticity index for the soil having a liquid limit of more than or equal to 20. For soil with a liquid limit of less than 20, the Euclidian norm (L_2 norm) and L_1 norm ratio increases at a liquid limit of less than 20, leading to the unrealistic computation of the plasticity index. The ratio of the Euclidian and Manhattan distance at various liquid limits is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 10: Comparison between determined and computed plasticity index ($R^2=0.988$ for the linear best-fit line)

Figure 11: The liquid limit and plasticity index with the best-fit curve (equation 5)

Figure 12: The relationship between the ratio of Euclidian and Manhattan distance and liquid limit

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of 204 Atterberg limits test results used for the development of the model and 74 soil used for validating this model, it can be seen that the model computes the plasticity index of the most inorganic clay reasonably well and within the statistical testing bound of ± 8 . Furthermore, for most inorganic clay, the plasticity index is a function of a liquid limit.

References:

1. Standard Specifications for Transportation Materials and Method of Sampling and Testing, Part II Tests (1995), AASHTO T90-94, Determining the Plastic Limit and Plasticity Index of Soils, American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials
2. Feng, T (2002), A linear log D- log W model for determination of consistency limits of soils, Canadian Geotechnical Journal, 38, 1335-1342.
3. Harison, JA, (1988), Using the BS cone penetrometer for the determination of plastic limit of soils, Geotechnique, Vol.38, No.3 pp433-438
4. Kayabali, K, Fener, M, Akturk, O, Ustun, B.A, (2016), Evaluation of undrained strength of fine-grained soil in consideration of soil plasticity, Earth Science
5. Maregesi, G, (2023), Plasticity index of Inorganic Clay, Advanced Engineering Solutions Journal vol.3/2023, Journal of Civil Engineering and Construction Technology
6. Maregesi, G, (2022), determination of the plasticity index using slope of the fall cone flow curve, Engineering Solutions Journal vol.23/2022, Journal of Civil Engineering and Construction Technology
7. O'Kelly, B.C, Vardanega, P.J, Haigh, S, K, (2018), Use of Fall Cones to determine Atterberg limits, a review, Geotechnique 68, No. 10, 843-856.
8. Prakash, K & Sridharan, A (1999), determination of the plasticity index from flow index. Geotech. Testing J.22.No.2, 169-175
9. Sharma, B & Bora, P.K, (2003) Plastic limit and Undrained shear strength of soil – Reappraisal, Journal of Geotechnical and Geoinvoromental Engineering
10. Towner, G.D (1973), An examination of the fall cone method for the determination of some strength properties of remoulded agricultural soils, Journal of soil science, Vol 24, NO.4, pp470-479